

EXTRACTION OF BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS FROM PLANT BY-PRODUCTS INTENDED FOR FISH FEED SUPPLEMENTS

**Stergiopoulos C.^{1*}, Dimitriadis T.¹, Polonyfi F.², Papadaki S.², Krokida M.¹, Plămadă D.³,
Calinoiu L.F.³, Vodnar D.C.³**

¹ Laboratory of Process Analysis and Design, School of Chemical Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Iroon Polytechniou 9, Zografou 15780, Athens, Greece

² DIGNITY PRIVATE COMPANY, 30-32 Leoforos Alexandrou Papagou, Zografou 157 71, Athens, Greece

³ Department of Food Science and Technology, University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine, Calea Mănăştur 3-5, 400372 Cluj-Napoca, Romania

Abstract

Aquaculture is a fast-growing sector playing an important role in the global food supply. The need to reduce the use of chemicals with the aim of supporting sustainable aquaculture and act against antimicrobial resistance is of critical importance. Several studies show that a combination of bioactive plant extracts can improve the health status and performance of farmed fish in a sustainable way. In this work, the potential of plant by-products to be valorized and used as fish feed additives was investigated. For that purpose, lemon (*Citrus x limon*) and orange (*Citrus x sinensis*) peels and a mix of them, as well as olive tree (*Olea europaea*) leaves of the greek cultivar Kolovi (*greek cv. Kolovi*) were used as raw materials for the extraction of bioactive compounds. Raw materials were processed with simultaneous ultrasonic-assisted and microwave-assisted extraction (UAE/MAE) at a constant solid to solvent ratio of 1:20. The influence of three different extraction solvents, namely water, ethanol/water 80:20 and ethyl acetate, to extraction efficiency and yield was also examined. It was proven that the most suitable extraction solvent for the recovery of bioactive compounds was the mixture of ethanol/water 80:20, as it resulted in greatest amounts of bioactives recovered and extraction yield in all cases. Superior antioxidant capacity and richer content in bioactive substances resulted from the olive leaves extract, followed by the lemon peels extract. The two aforementioned extracts show great potential to be used as fish feed additives, with many benefits, not only for fish health, but also for fish aquacultures and the environment.

Keywords: *fish feed, sustainable aquaculture, fish feed additives, bioactive plant extracts*

*Corresponding author: Stergiopoulos Chrysanthos (chrisxp3@hotmail.com)

1. Introduction

Several plant extracts are considered promising feed additives in fish nutrition with high potential to enhance weight gain, feed efficiency, and/or disease resistance in aquaculture fish. Natural extracts from plants have been reported to favor various activities like anti-stress, growth promotion, appetite stimulation, enhancement of tonicity and immunostimulation, maturation of culture species and anti-pathogen properties in fish aquacultures due to active principles such as alkaloids, terpenoids, tannins, saponins, glycosides, flavonoids, phenolics, steroids or essential oil (Reverter *et al.* 2014). These compounds can also be produced as secondary metabolites and protect cells against microbial infections, exerting several biological properties, mainly antioxidant and anti-inflammatory. Moreover, their use could reduce costs of treatment and be more environmentally friendly as such compounds tend to be more biodegradable than synthetic molecules and they are less likely to produce drug resistance in parasites due to the high diversity of plant extract molecules (Xavier *et al.* 2021).

Polyphenols are the largest category of phytochemicals produced by plants to defend themselves against bacteria, viruses, and fungi. Animal and human epidemiologic studies show that various polyphenols have antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties that could have preventive and/or therapeutic effects for cardiovascular disease, neurodegenerative disorders, cancer, and obesity (Cory *et al.* 2018). Phenolic acids and flavonoids represent the two main classes. Extracting polyphenols is challenging because extraction techniques should not alter compound quality. Technologies for extracting polyphenolic compounds from plants include conventional techniques, such as percolation, decoction, heat reflux extraction, Soxhlet extraction and maceration, as well as advanced techniques like ultrasound-assisted extraction, microwave-assisted extraction, supercritical fluid extraction, high-voltage electric discharge, pulse electric field extraction and enzyme-assisted extraction. Advanced techniques are 32–36% more efficient with approximately 15 times less energy consumption and producing higher-quality extracts (Sridhar *et al.* 2021).

In this work, plant by-products, namely orange (*Citrus x sinensis*) and lemon (*Citrus x limon*) peels, as well as olive tree (*Olea europaea*, *greek cv. Kolovi*) leaves, were used as primary sources for the extraction of bioactive compounds. For that purpose, simultaneous microwave-ultrasound assisted extraction was applied, using

three different extraction solvents. For each extract, total antioxidant capacity, phenolic content and various bioactive compounds were determined. Results were compared with each other, in order to identify the extracts of highest quality obtained by the corresponding optimum extraction conditions that could be used as fish feed additives.

2. Material and Methods

Lemon (*Citrus x limon*) and orange (*Citrus x sinensis*) peels were purchased from a local market in Cluj-Napoca, Romania. Natural Food Additives G.P, Athens, Greece, supplied olive tree (*Olea europaea*, greek cv. *Kolovi*) leaves. Prior to extraction, raw materials were dried at 42°C overnight in a BOV-V/VL Vacuum Drying Oven (Biobase, Jinan, Shandong, China) to constant weight. Dried material was further homogenized by grinding.

Simultaneous ultrasonic-assisted extraction (UAE) and microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) was conducted utilizing an XO-SM50 Ultrasonic Microwave Reaction System (Nanjing Xianou Instruments Manufacture Co. Ltd., Nanjing, China). The system operated at a frequency of 25 kHz, with a power setting of 450 W and a temperature of 25°C with the overall extraction duration set at 15 minutes. The samples, maintained at a solid-to-solvent ratio of 1:20 g dry weight per mL solvent, were subjected to the extraction process in a beaker.

Ethyl acetate, ethanol/water 80:20 and water were used as extraction solvents. Prior to analysis, extracts were centrifuged using a Centrifugator NF400 (Nüve, Akara, Türkiye) and filtered using 0.45 µm MF-Millipore™ Membrane Filters (Sigma Aldrich, Saint Louis, MO, USA). Following the extraction procedure, the samples were stored at -20°C in a freezer until further characterization.

Extracts were fully dried using a BÜCHI R-200 Rotavapor System (BÜCHI Labortechnik, Flawil, Switzerland) and % extraction yield (% EY) was calculated with the use of equation (1):

$$\% EY = \frac{m_{dry\ extract}}{m_{dry\ material}} \% \quad (1)$$

where $m_{dry\ extract}$ corresponds to the mass of solid remaining after the solvent evaporation $m_{dry\ material}$ to the initial mass of dried raw material used for the extraction process.

Antioxidant capacity of the extracts was determined using trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity assay (TEAC), with 2,2'-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) used as radical and 6-hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethylchroman-2-carboxylic acid (trolox) as antioxidant agent. Radical scavenging of DPPH by the extracts was determined spectrometrically at 515 nm after 30 min reaction according equation (2):

$$\% DPPH\ inhibition = 1 - \frac{A_{t=30min}}{A_{t=0}} \% \quad (2)$$

where $A_{t=30min}$ the absorbance of the sample after 60 min of reaction and $A_{t=0}$ the initial absorption of the sample. A Bel Photonics M51 UV-Vis Spectrometer (Bel Engineering s.r.l., Monza, Italy) was used for the absorbance measurements and % DPPH inhibition was converted to trolox equivalents via corresponding trolox standard curves.

High-performance liquid chromatography with a diode-array detector (HPLC-DAD) was used in order to detect the main bioactive compounds of the extracts. The HPLC apparatus consisted of a Prominence-i LC-2030 3D gradient pump and a diode array detector (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan). A Kromasil C18 column (5 µm, 250 × 4.6 mm, Nouryon AB, Göteborg, Sweden) was used under thermostated conditions at 30 °C. The samples were injected after filtration with 0.45 µm, PVDF syringe filters (Teknokroma, Barcelona, Spain) and the flow rate was 1 mL/min. The solvent system consisted of water (A), methanol (B), acetonitrile (C) and isopropanol (D), each containing 0.2% trifluoroacetic acid. The initial composition of the mobile phase was 90% A, 6% B, 4% C and 0% D. With linear gradients, the composition changed to 85% A, 9% B, 6% C and 0% D within 5 min, 71% A, 17.4% B, 11.6% C and 0% D within 30 min, 0% A, 85% B, 15% C and 0% D within 60 min and 0% A, 60% B, 0% C and 40% D within 70 min. The injection volume was 20 µL, while the elution of compounds was monitored at 280, 360 and 445 nm. System control, data acquisition, and data processing were performed using the LabSolutions Workstation (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan). The identification of compounds was performed according to the UV-Vis spectra of the peaks, retention times, use of internal standards, and comparison with literature data. Compounds were quantified according to the calibration curves obtained with the respective authentic reference compounds. All calibration curves were obtained in the range of 20–200 mg/L analyzing four concentrations (20, 50, 100, 200 mg/L) from duplicate samples. The detection of compounds was performed at the previously

mentioned wavelengths and the produced linear equations presented $R^2 > 0.998$. Total flavonoids were determined as rutin equivalents, phenolic acids as chlorogenic acid equivalents and total carotenoids as lutein equivalents.

3. Results

Total quantities of extracted bioactive substances, antioxidant capacities and extraction yields are shown in Table 1. All results are expressed in mg/gr dry extract, except from the extraction yield that is expressed as % percentage. A graphical illustration of the results is also included in Figure 1.

Table 1. Quantitative results of the analysis of extracts: total bioactives, antioxidant capacity and yield

mg/gr dry extract	Olive Leaves 1:20			Orange Peels 1:20			Lemon Peels 1:20			Mixed Peels 1:20		
	Water	Ethanol/Water	Ethyl Acetate	Water	Ethanol/Water	Ethyl Acetate	Water	Ethanol/Water	Ethyl Acetate	Water	Ethanol/Water	Ethyl Acetate
Phenolic acids	0.82	1.37	n/d	6.32	3.11	n/d	1.40	2.80	n/d	3.70	2.82	n/d
Total Flavonoids	0.41	9.33	1.14	3.25	7.77	5.36	7.86	15.5	1.11	4.94	9.45	5.44
Total Carotenoids	n/d	1.17	0.87	n/d	n/q	n/q	n/d	n/q	n/q	n/d	n/q	n/q
Trolox Equivalents	57.4	129	50.9	6.35	4.82	4.94	9.8	10.5	5.18	7.60	6.61	1.00
Oleuropein	43.1	185	89.6	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d
Hydroxy tyrosols	30.4	26.2	6.99	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d
EY %	16.3	17.9	8.57	28.6	42.4	8.78	9.7	27.0	5.96	23.0	37.1	8.95

n/d: not detected, n/q: not quantifiable

Figure 1. Comparative quantities of bioactive compounds extracted, antioxidant capacity and extraction yields

From the results of Table 1 and as shown in Figure 1, it becomes evident that the most appropriate solvent of the ones tested in this work for the extraction of bioactive compounds is the mixture of ethanol/water 80:20. The use of this solvent mixture leads to extracts that are richer in bioactive substances and of increased antioxidant

capacity. Extraction yield is also greater with the use of ethanol/water 80:20 in all cases of raw materials. However, the extract that proved superior regarding its antioxidant activity (expressed in trolox equivalents) was the olive leaves extract. This can be attributed to the fact that apart from phenolic acids and flavonoids that are present in all extracts, olive leaves extract contains also other important categories of antioxidants, such as carotenoids, oleuropein and hydroxytyrosolic compounds that exhibit strong antioxidant activity. On the other hand, the lemon peels extract showed also good antioxidant activity. The differences between the two aforementioned cases can become clearer from their chromatographic analysis, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Chromatographic analysis of lemon peels and olive leaves extracts at 360 nm

As seen in Figure 1, olive leaves extract includes oleuropein and more concentration of carotenoids, although the latter compounds can also be found in the lemon peels extract but in scarce, not detectable amounts. Lemon peels extract, however, includes more phenolics and flavonoids than the olive leaves.

Apart from their differences, both extracts show great potential to be used as fish feed additives, however, toxicological and antimicrobial activity of the extracts should also be investigated. Valorization of plant by-products in such a way will bring many benefits to fish aquacultures, as plant extracts can replace the use of

synthetic drugs, decrease the environmental pollution, contribute to the health and well-being of fish and lead to a sustainable way of fish feed management.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101086261.

References

- Cory H., Passarelli S., Szeto J., Tamez M., Mattei J. (2018). The Role of Polyphenols in Human Health and Food Systems: A Mini-Review. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, 21, 5:87. 10.3389/fnut.2018.00087.
- Reverter M., Bontemps N., Lecchini D., Banaigs B., Sasal P. (2014). Use of plant extracts in fish aquaculture as an alternative to chemotherapy: Current status and future perspectives. *Aquaculture*, 433, 50-61. 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2014.05.048.
- Sridhar A., Ponnuchamy M., Kumar P.S., Kapoor A., Vo D.N., Prabhakar S. (2021). Techniques and modeling of polyphenol extraction from food: a review. *Environmental Chemistry Letters*, 19(4), 3409-3443. 10.1007/s10311-021-01217-8.
- Xavier M.J., Conceição L.E.C., Valente L.M.P., Colen R., Rodrigues A.C.M., Rocha R.J.M., Custódio L., Carballo C., Manchado, M., Engrola S. (2021). Dietary Natural Plant Extracts Can Promote Growth and Modulate Oxidative Status of Senegalese Sole Postlarvae under Standard/Challenge Conditions. *Animals*, 11, 1398. 10.3390/ani11051398.